

Relaxation and Attention: The Impacts of Place on Brain Activity Captured by EEG

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Abstract. To further explore the neurocognitive impact of place, this study investigates the impacts of a variety of places in urban and natural settings on brain activity. In particular, the percentage change in relative power of two frequency bands, alpha and low beta, is examined. These two frequency bands are associated with relaxed wakefulness and attention. Preliminary results show that natural green space, historic public market, and downtown at night in Seattle may make participants focused and relaxed, but further examinations will be needed.

Keywords. Place, brain activity, EEG

1. Introduction

There has been a surge of interest in research on the cognitive and psychological impacts of the environment on brain activity and how the human brain responds to place and space (Aspinall, Mavros, Coyne, & Roe, 2015; Hilton, Kapaj, & Fabrikant, 2025; Lobben, Lawrence, & Limpisathian, 2019; Qin, Dong, & Huang, 2023). Advances in neural and location tracking technologies have contributed considerably to this research trend by offering research toolkits and underpinning emerging approaches at high spatial and temporal resolutions and within a portable experimental paradigm. Mobile electroencephalogram (EEG) outside clinical settings is one of the neural technologies increasingly used in urban and geospatial studies (Mavros, Austwick, & Smith, 2016). For example, mobile EEG was applied to learn the influence of walking or sitting in different urban environments on brain activity (Lin, et al., 2020; Neale, et al., 2020; Olszewska-Guizzo, Sia, Fogel, & Ho, 2020). The examined urban settings frequently involve urban green space and commercial districts. Yet, other kinds of urban and natural settings were studied less often. There are various places people

Published in "Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Location Based Services (LBS 2025)", edited by Juha Oksanen, Henrikki Tenkanen, Pyry Kettunen and Ville Mäkinen, LBS 2025 7-9 May 2025 Otaniemi, Espoo, Finland.

This contribution underwent double-blind peer review based on the paper. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15351355>
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may visit in their daily lives, and these places also shape people’s brain activity.

To fill in this research gap, this study investigates the impacts of a variety of places in urban and natural settings on brain activities, which are alpha and low beta waves, captured by EEG. The two brainwaves are active when people are awake and are indicators of relaxation and attention. Alpha waves are associated with relaxed wakefulness (Mikicin & Kowalczyk, 2015). Low beta waves are dominant in those who are focused and not stressed (Díaz M, et al., 2019). They help reveal whether people are relaxed and focused in a place. A lab experiment was designed and conducted for data collection. The findings might contribute to improving location-based services with a focus on the impacts of place and environment on individuals’ brain activities and psychological well-being.

2. Methods

2.1. Place selection

Figure 1. Geographic scenes illustrated in the first frame of each video (Source: author).

Various places in Seattle, USA, were chosen to include as many urban and natural settings as possible. These places are on the campus of the University of Washington (UW), in the university commercial district, in parks, at urban tourist attraction sites, in bustling downtown areas, and along roads associated with homelessness and prostitution. Places near the university and in the parks were recorded by the author in March and June 2023 using a hand-held camera (DJI Osmo Pocket) and a location tracking app

(Strava) on the mobile phone. Other places were recorded after 2020 by YouTubers who took a walking tour of the city. There were 26 videos, each edited into a 1-minute video clip, providing a first-person perspective for moving through space.

2.2. Experimental procedures

The experiment, approved by the UW Institutional Review Board, was conducted in a lab between June and August 2023. At the beginning of the experiment, participants signed the consent form and completed a pre-experiment questionnaire to report on their mood and health status at the moment. Next, participants wore an EEG headset (EMOTIV EPOC X) with the help of the author. They watched 26 1-minute videos in the same order on a 27-inch computer screen while having their brain signals recorded. Each video started with the video number for 2 seconds, a fixation cross for 5 seconds, and the video clip for 1 minute, and ended with a fixation cross for another 5 seconds. Videos were played without sound to direct attention to the visual details of different locations. The participants were instructed to relax and sit still when the video clip was on. Once all videos were played, the author stopped the EEG recording and helped the participants take off the EEG headset. The participants then completed a post-experiment questionnaire about demographics and perception of places following a short break. Finally, the participants had an interview with the author to elaborate on their perception and related experiences about places in the videos.

2.3. Data analysis

A total of 37 undergraduate and graduate students in different majors at UW participated in the experiment. Based on data quality, responses from 34 participants were considered valid.

The EEG headset used in the experiment has 14 channels, including AF3, F7, F3, FC5, T7, P7, O1, O2, P8, T8, FC6, F4, F8, AF4. EEG signals are sampled at 256 Hz per channel. They were preprocessed using the EEGLAB toolbox in MATLAB R2024a. EEG signals were filtered with a frequency range between 0.5 and 45 Hz. Bad channels were removed if they were flat for more than 5 seconds, the high-frequency noise standard deviation was larger than 4, and correlation with nearby channels was lower than 0.85. EEG signals were then re-referenced to the common average. An independent component analysis (ICA) was performed using an adaptive mixture independent component analysis (AMICA) algorithm. Independent components (ICs) classified into eye and muscle activities with probabilities higher than 0.7 were rejected. Lastly, the removed channels were interpolated using spherical interpolation.

The band power of alpha (8-12 Hz) and low beta (12-19 Hz) was computed per video per participant per channel using Welch's periodogram. Their relative values were adopted to compare across videos and participants. All channel power was aggregated per participant per video by averaging. To infer the changes in brain activities due to the places presented in videos, the percentage change in power was calculated as below.

$$\text{prctchange} = 100 * (\text{power}_{\text{video}} - \text{power}_{\text{baseline}}) / \text{power}_{\text{baseline}}$$

Each 5-second fixation cross phase right before each video served as its baseline phase. To test whether the impact of each place in the video is statistically different, ANOVA (if significant) followed by Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test, was run for both frequency bands.

3. Preliminary results

The results of the percentage change in relative alpha band power indicate that natural green space, downtown Seattle at night, historic public market, and waterfront might be relaxing to participants (Figure 2). Their pairwise differences with other places are significant and noticeable (Table 1). The results of the percentage change in relative low beta band power imply that natural green space, historic public market, and downtown Seattle at night may make participants focused and not agitated (Figure 3). Their pairwise differences with other places are also significant and large in effect size (Table 2).

Figure 2. Percentage change in relative alpha band power per video (Source: author).

Figure 3. Percentage change in relative low beta band power per video (Source: author).

Table 1. Tukey's HSD test results for alpha band (Source: author).

Group1	Group2	Mean difference	Adjusted p-value	CI_lower	CI_upper	Reject	Cohen's d
9	22	72.8621	0.0015	16.6738	129.0503	TRUE	-0.83267
9	24	98.9728	0	42.7846	155.1611	TRUE	-0.99229
10	22	68.7986	0.0039	12.6104	124.9869	TRUE	-0.77225
10	24	94.9094	0	38.7212	151.0976	TRUE	-0.93844
11	21	62.4824	0.0151	6.2941	118.6706	TRUE	-1.13603
11	22	95.2558	0	39.0675	151.444	TRUE	-1.12675
11	24	121.3665	0	65.1783	177.5547	TRUE	-1.24925
11	26	63.972	0.0111	7.7838	120.1602	TRUE	-1.0106
12	22	80.8968	0.0002	24.7086	137.085	TRUE	-0.94396
12	24	107.0076	0	50.8193	163.1958	TRUE	-1.09011
16	22	65.114	0.0087	8.9257	121.3022	TRUE	-0.73109
16	24	91.2247	0	35.0365	147.413	TRUE	-0.9022
20	21	59.0946	0.0294	2.9064	115.2829	TRUE	-1.04956
20	22	91.868	0	35.6798	148.0562	TRUE	-1.07581
20	24	117.9788	0	61.7905	174.167	TRUE	-1.20514
20	26	60.5843	0.0221	4.396	116.7725	TRUE	-0.9402
21	24	58.8841	0.0306	2.6959	115.0724	TRUE	-0.54685
22	23	-73.0637	0.0014	-129.252	-16.8755	TRUE	0.826914
22	25	-60.3071	0.0233	-116.495	-4.1188	TRUE	0.65431
23	24	99.1745	0	42.9863	155.3627	TRUE	-0.9869
24	25	-86.4178	0	-142.606	-30.2296	TRUE	0.832072
24	26	-57.3945	0.0403	-113.583	-1.2063	TRUE	0.511784

Table 2. Tukey's HSD test results for in low beta band (Source: author).

<i>Group1</i>	<i>Group2</i>	<i>Mean difference</i>	<i>Adjusted p-value</i>	<i>CI_lower</i>	<i>CI_upper</i>	<i>Reject</i>	<i>Cohen's d</i>
9	21	64.4521	0.0054	10.6573	118.2469	TRUE	-1.03985
9	22	71.5343	0.0009	17.7395	125.3291	TRUE	-0.9514
9	24	138.0118	0	84.217	191.8066	TRUE	-1.22205
10	21	54.0054	0.0481	0.2105	107.8002	TRUE	-0.8578
10	22	61.0875	0.0115	7.2927	114.8823	TRUE	-0.80383
10	24	127.5651	0	73.7703	181.3599	TRUE	-1.12418
11	21	70.8792	0.0011	17.0844	124.674	TRUE	-1.19612
11	22	77.9613	0.0002	24.1665	131.7562	TRUE	-1.06856
11	24	144.4389	0	90.6441	198.2337	TRUE	-1.29585
12	21	56.5608	0.0295	2.766	110.3556	TRUE	-0.88602
12	22	63.6429	0.0065	9.8481	117.4377	TRUE	-0.82949
12	24	130.1205	0	76.3257	183.9153	TRUE	-1.14177
16	24	117.5431	0	63.7483	171.3379	TRUE	-1.02332
20	21	68.453	0.0021	14.6582	122.2478	TRUE	-1.12206
20	22	75.5352	0.0003	21.7404	129.33	TRUE	-1.01544
20	24	142.0128	0	88.218	195.8076	TRUE	-1.26343
21	23	-57.8681	0.0227	-111.663	-4.0733	TRUE	0.901703
21	24	73.5597	0.0006	19.7649	127.3545	TRUE	-0.59335
21	25	-63.7201	0.0064	-117.515	-9.9253	TRUE	1.013777
22	23	-64.9503	0.0048	-118.745	-11.1555	TRUE	0.843428
22	24	66.4776	0.0034	12.6828	120.2724	TRUE	-0.50717
22	25	-70.8023	0.0011	-124.597	-17.0075	TRUE	0.932725
23	24	131.4279	0	77.6331	185.2227	TRUE	-1.15132
24	25	-137.28	0	-191.075	-83.485	TRUE	1.21041
24	26	-117.263	0	-171.058	-63.4686	TRUE	1.012942

4. Discussion

The results shed light on the impacts of different places on participants' brain activities, indicating the state of being relaxed and/or focused. To further understand what exact brain states participants might have, other frequency bands such as theta and gamma can be examined, and other measurements such as frontal alpha, theta/beta ratio, and frontal asymmetry can be calculated. To further model place context, video content can be quantified to measure spatial elements and human activities. Participants' brain responses in a lab setting might be somewhat different from in-situ settings. It would be meaningful to compare the results of different experimental settings (e.g., VR or the real world).

Importantly, knowing how different places affect brain activities might be conducive to recommending services and activities (e.g., those that can increase relaxation and restore attention) based on a user's location at a specific place. In addition, brain activities can be valuable neurophysiological

feedback to place making and place improvement, making our places not just functional but also feel right.

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